

Teacher Disciplinary Techniques And Classroom Control In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between teacher disciplinary techniques and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Three objectives with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses guided the study. A correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprised all the 5,833 teachers of 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select a sample size of 583 teachers representing 10% of the entire population. Two questionnaire instruments titled: Teacher Disciplinary Techniques Scale (TDTS) and Classroom Control Scale (CCS) were used for this study. Cronbach alpha reliability test was conducted to ascertain the reliability of the instruments, of which the reliability coefficients of Teacher Disciplinary Techniques Scale and Classroom Control Scale were 0.89 and 0.83 respectively. Research questions were answered with the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, while same correlation statistics was used to test the corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a strong and significant relationship between, drafting of classroom rules, changing of student's seat arrangement, rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Thus, it was concluded that teacher disciplinary techniques significantly relate with classroom control in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. Based on the findings and conclusion, the study recommended among others that teachers should always ensure that students are given the opportunity to participate in the drafting of the classroom rules, as it will help them to comply considering that they were part of those that made the rules. Also, teachers should ensure that they adopt disciplinary technique like changing of student's seat arrangement as it has proven to be effective in classroom control.

Keywords: Teacher, Disciplinary Technique, Classroom Control

INTRODUCTION

The education sector of any nation plays a significant role in the sustenance of other sectors. The education does not only supply the manpower needed to service the other sectors of the nation or economy but also assists in the achievement of the goals and objectives of these other sectors. In educational systems, world over, the ways academic activity of the school is coordinated makes the difference. The goals of national educational systems and indeed national development becomes a mirage if there is no proper classroom control. Classroom control is one of the most pressing issues in school management as it concerns administrators, teachers and students. This is quite imperative because no meaningful academic achievement can be attained in any educational setting where there is disorder, disobedience, anarchy and lack of self-control among students.

Classroom control can be defined as the orderly control of students, the class environment and teaching materials in order to obtain the desired learning objectives which can enhance the academic achievement of students. Akpakwu (2022), defines classroom control as the orderly control of the learners, teaching materials and teaching aids in order to obtain the desired learning objectives. Classroom control has to do with managing what goes on in the classroom as it affects teaching and learning. The teacher manages the physical as well as the psychological environment to create an atmosphere that is conducive for learning. Classroom control according to Igbacha (2016) is a process involving planning, organizing, coordinating, motivating and controlling the actions of learners and materials in order to achieve instructional objectives. The art of classroom control encompasses all the functions of a classroom teacher in instructional procedure. Such activities include lesson planning and presentation, organization of the classroom facilities, coordination of learning activities, management of instructional materials and disciplinary techniques (Nwankwo, 2014). However, this paper would focus on disciplinary techniques of a teacher.

Disciplinary techniques are vital tools for classroom control. In the school system, discipline is necessary for the effective classroom control, if the goals of the schools are to be accomplished. The concept teacher disciplinary techniques can be defined as elements of teacher managerial tasks that involves the measurement and correction of activities of the students to make sure that the objectives of the school and plans desired to attain them are accomplished. Discipline is among the most difficult and unpleasant part of teaching profession considering many students misbehaviour in the classroom. Students' misbehaviour is a prevailing problem affecting not only classroom activities but also the students as well. Students' misconduct in the classroom interferes with teaching and learning and is thought to be precursor to later school dropout and similar negative social outcomes.

The indiscipline problem in schools is ranked as a major problem among students of secondary schools in Nigeria. More than ever before, teachers are faced with critical problems in their classrooms, and are confronted (on a daily basis) with unacceptable learner behaviour and threatening situations. Disruptive behaviour is a concern to teachers and parents and to fellow students, whose education may be adversely affected. So it cannot be ignored, and teachers must tailor a well-understood sound behaviour and discipline technique. Disciplinary techniques in class organisation include any rational approach used or adopted by teachers to overcome the problems of student's misconduct. These techniques are plan of action designed to achieve classroom control or conducive classroom environment where teaching and learning can take place. Disciplinary techniques are approaches occasionally adopted by teachers to correct a situation where a student has broken the rules or is not putting in the required amount of effort in the classroom.

The approach taken towards disciplinary action often determines the classroom effectiveness. Many traditional approaches to discipline are negative, punitive and reactive, which result in bad feelings for all parties involved. A positive approach to discipline involves a process designed to solve performance problems and encourage good performance. The basic theory behind the positive discipline approach is that when a student is treated as an adult who must solve a problem, rather than as a child who must be punished, the student is more likely to respond positively and correct the problem. However, before any disciplinary technique is required, there must be acceptance and understanding of the rules of conduct and the disciplinary system by both teachers and students. Students should know exactly what is expected of them and what the consequences will be if they do not meet those expectations. The rules should be consistent and fair. The discipline system will be more effective when the disciplinary technique is meant to tackle the root cause of indiscipline behaviour of the students. There are many teacher's disciplinary techniques for classroom control, but for this study the researcher considered few as identified by some scholars. Nakpodia (2010) and Ezeugbor and Eboatu (2018) noted that some teachers' disciplinary strategies include; drafting of classroom rules, changing of students seat arrangement and rewards.

Drafting of classroom rule is defined as the setting of rules and guidelines that are imposed by the teacher that the class must follow. These rules are designed to assist the teacher in behaviour management and ensure there is a positive environment for learning where all students feel comfortable and safe. Some authors like Kohzadi and Hafezi (2021), Arasa and K'Obonyo (2019) and Newstrom and Davis (2019)

who conducted some study have come to attest that drafting of classroom rules to high extent promotes classroom control. According to Kohzadi and Hafezi (2021), creating of class rules focuses on determining the direction of students' behaviour, teaching coordination and classroom control. When rules are set or made, it helps to guide the students towards the accomplishment of their academic pursuit and for effective classroom control. More so, Amadi and Udisi (2021) opined that drafting of classroom rules ensures cohesion of activities in the classroom and enables maximum compliance from students with limited teacher effort. It calls for just-in-time control of all processes as to cooperatively achieve result. Without availability of rules, classroom control will be difficult to achieve.

Furthermore, changing of student seat which is another teacher's disciplinary strategy has to do with moving a student away from his or usual sitting place and position that seem to be aiding the student misbehaviour to a different seat. Teachers adopt this strategy when they find out the sitting position of a student may be disrupting teaching and learning process in the classroom or distracting student from participating in some classroom activities. This could be resorted to when some other methods of discipline have failed (Ngware et al., 2018). Scholars like Denton (2022) and Taiwo and Opadokun (2022) in their respective studies found that changing of students' seat arrangement has a positive and significant influence on classroom control. More so, Taiwo and Opadokun (2022) asserted that that if the classroom setting is orderly, beautiful, and comfortable in terms of seat arrangement, lighting, organization and temperature conditions, students will be made happy and willing to learn than to indulge wrong doing. However, a poorly arranged classroom, which does not have good seat arrangement can lead to boredom, fatigue, indiscipline, and negative learning attitudes on the part of the students which could necessitate misconduct.

In addition, reward is doing something or giving something to student to increase appropriate behaviour or skill. There is a belief that reward is not only right and desirable but also indispensable. It can be given for attendance, conduct, progress, games, badges and certificates may be given as rewards. Some scholars have also reported in their studies that, the use of reward helps in the control of classroom behaviours of students (Rahimi & Karkami, 2021; Reinke, et al., 2022; Dyah, 2023). According to Shah and McNeil (2018) quantitative findings, rewards help teachers overcome students' social and behavioural problems in the classroom. This was reported by a majority of 78.01% (Strongly Agree 40.31%; Agree 37.70%) of the respondents in the study conducted. Nevertheless, Ajibola and Hamadi (2021) observed that some of these techniques have proven to have a positive significant relationship with classroom control. Also, preliminary investigation from researchers has shown that the benefits accruing from teachers' disciplinary strategies for attainment of classroom control cannot be overemphasized. The significant progression in classroom control as asserted by scholars has brought about tremendous benefits to school especially in the area of achieving effective teaching and learning. It is against this background that this study sought to examine if these teachers' disciplinary techniques relate with classroom control in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The classroom play an important role in the learning process of the student, their time management and respect for others as well as in regulating their conduct. However, the current situation in Rivers State education system as alleged by concerned individuals in the state has shown that indiscipline among students in the classroom is escalating rapidly with notable strikes like noise making, bullying, theft, molestation, cultism, sexual related activities, vandalism of school property, general refusal to follow rules and regulations as well as increasing alcoholism. An increasing numbering of secondary school head teachers and teachers are reporting a wide range of potentially disruptive behaviors in the classrooms and around the schools. Many students are seen loitering in streets, villages, game/cinema halls and other places in their uniforms, which affects their behaviour during class time, causing them to violate classroom rules and regulations resulting in poor time management and classroom control.

This has therefore created a big concern for head teachers, teachers and other stakeholders about the lack of opportunity for students to concentrate on the academic work for attainment good performance in their tests, internal exams and national level examination as well as becoming better citizens of the society. The effect of this increasing trend of indiscipline act in the classrooms is what prompted the researcher to

carry out this study to ascertain if there is a relationship that exist between teacher disciplinary techniques and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between teacher disciplinary techniques and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In specific terms, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. determine the relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the relationship between changing of student's seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. find out the relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between changing of student's seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
1. There is no significant relationship between changing of student's seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between reinforcement/rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlation design to ascertain if there is a relationship among the variables using a quantitative method of research. The population of this study was made up of all the 5,833 teachers (i.e. 2,844 male and 2,989 female) of 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. (Source: Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2024). The sample for this study was 583 teachers representing 10% of the entire population. The sample size was drawn from the entire population using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. This ensured that all members of the population are given equal opportunity of being selected. Questionnaire was the research instrument for the study which was titled: Teacher Disciplinary Techniques Scale (TDTS) and Classroom Control Scale (CCS). The instruments have two sections (A and B). Section A elicited demographic information from the respondents, while section B elicited information on TDTS and CCS. These two instruments were coded in line with the modified four-point Likert rating scale as follows; Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 Points, Agree (A) = 3 Points, Disagree (D) = 2 Points, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 Point respectively. Cronbach Alpha reliability statistics was used to test the reliability of the two instruments. The reliability coefficients of Teacher Disciplinary Technique Scale and Classroom Control Scale are 0.89 and 0.83. For the data that were analyzed, research question 1 to 3 were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), while same statistics was used to test the corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 significance level with the help of Statistical Package in Social Science (SPSS). Correlation coefficients between 0.90 – 1.00 were considered to be a Very High (VH), 0.70 – 0.80 are High (H) while correlation coefficients between 0.50 – 0.60 were Moderate (M) and between 0.30 – 0.40 were Low (L) while below 0.20 (< 0.20) were Very Low (VL). As part of data collection efforts, the researcher designed and distributed 583

copies of the questionnaire to the respondents, 561 copies were retrieved and found suitable for analysis resulting in 96% retrieval rate.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Showing the Relationship between Drafting of Classroom Rules and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Drafting of Classroom Rules	561	559	0.751	High
(Positive Relationship)				
Classroom Control	561			

Data on Table 1 reveal a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.75$. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in drafting of classroom rules leads to corresponding increase in classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between changing of student’s seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Showing the Relationship between Changing of Student’s Seat Arrangement and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Changing of Student’s Seat Arrangement	561	559	0.713	High
(Positive Relationship)				
Classroom Control	561			

Data on Table 2 reveal a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.71$. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between changing of student’s seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in changing of student’s seat arrangement leads to corresponding increase in classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Showing the Relationship between Rewards and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	Decision
Rewards	561	559	0.874	High
(Positive Relationship)				
Classroom Control	561			

Data on Table 3 reveal a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.87$. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary

schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in rewards of students leads to corresponding increase in classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Drafting of Classroom Rules and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Drafting of Classroom Rules	561	559	0.751	0.001	0.05	Reject Ho ₁
Classroom Control	561					

For hypothesis 1 tested, it is revealed also from Table 4 that the correlation for hypothesis one shows a significant correlation at $r = .751$ where $p\text{-value} = 0.001$ ($P < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value} 0.001$ is less than the alpha level 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between changing of student’s seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Changing of Student’s Seat Arrangement and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	n	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Changing of Student’s Seat Arrangement	561	559	0.713	0.000	0.05	Reject Ho ₂
Classroom Control	561					

For hypothesis 1 tested, it is revealed also from Table 5 that the correlation for hypothesis two shows a significant correlation at $r = .713$, where $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ ($P < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value} 0.000$ is less than the alpha level of 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between changing of student’s seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Test of Hypothesis on the Relationship between Rewards and Classroom Control in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variables	N	df	r	p-value	alpha level	Decision
Rewards	561	559	0.874	0.000	0.05	Reject Ho ₃
Classroom Control	561					

For hypothesis 3 tested, it is revealed also from Table 6 that the correlation for hypothesis three shows a significant correlation at $r = .874$ where $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ ($P < 0.05$). Since the $p\text{-value} 0.000$ is less than the alpha level 0.05, we therefore reject the null hypothesis, thus, there is a significant relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The first finding of this study revealed that there is high and positive relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, a corresponding hypothesis tested showed that there is a significant relationship between drafting of classroom rules and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings are in line with Kohzadi and Hafezi (2021), Arasa and K'Obonyo (2019) and Newstrom and Davis (2019) who empirical and scholarly contributions to knowledge attest that drafting of classroom rules to great extent promotes classroom management.

Also in line with the findings, Kohzadi and Hafezi (2021) found that most teachers believe that creating of class rules focuses on determining the direction of students' behaviour, teaching coordination and classroom control. When rules are set or made, it helps to guide the students towards the accomplishment of their academic pursuit and for effective classroom control. More so, Amadi and Udisi (2021) in their empirical study found that drafting of classroom rules ensures cohesion of activities in the classroom and enables maximum compliance from students with limited teacher effort. It calls for just-in-time control of all processes as to cooperatively achieve result. Without availability of rules, classroom control will be difficult to achieve.

The second finding of the study showed that there is high and positive relationship between changing of students' seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, a corresponding hypothesis tested revealed that there is a significant relationship between changing of students' seat arrangement and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers South-East Senatorial District. These findings are in agreement with Ngware et al. (2018), Denton (2022) and Taiwo and Opadokun (2022) who in their empirical studies found that changing of students' seat arrangement has a positive and significant influence on classroom control. Taiwo and Opadokun (2022) also in their empirical work found that if the classroom setting is orderly, beautiful, and comfortable in terms of seat arrangement, lighting, organization and temperature conditions, students will be made happy and willing to learn than to indulge wrong doing. However, a poorly arranged classroom, which does not have good seat arrangement can lead to boredom, fatigue, indiscipline, and negative learning attitudes on the part of the students which could necessitate misconduct.

In addition, in line with the finding, Denton (2022) found that the arrangement of students' seats should be such that the students will not have the opportunity to disrupt teaching and learning activities in the classroom or for them to misbehave considering the positive relationship between these variables. He buttresses that the seating arrangement of every classroom is the first and most important disciplinary

technique of teachers or point of concern in classroom control. This is because the arrangement of seats in the classroom has been viewed as an important factor for motivating students to learn or deterring them from misbehaving.

The third finding of the study showed that there is high and positive relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. More so, a corresponding hypothesis tested showed that there is a significant relationship between rewards and classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers South-East Senatorial District. These findings are in consonance with Shah and McNeil (2018), Skinner in Diedrich (2020), Coe (2021), Rahimi and Karkami (2021), Reinke, et al (2022), and Dyah (2023), who in their various empirical studies reported that the use of reward helps in the control of classroom behaviours of students. Shah and McNeil (2018) quantitative findings in a study conducted confirms that rewards help teachers overcome students' social and behavioural problems in the classroom. This was reported by a majority of 78.01% (Strongly Agree 40.31%; Agree 37.70%) of the respondents in the study conducted.

More so, Guner (2022) in his empirical study found that in Turkey schools, rewards are effective in managing students' behaviour, which results in controlled learning environment. Rahimi and Karkami (2021) also agrees when they found that reward is an effective strategy used by teachers to strengthen student behaviour to enhance classroom control. Ajibola and Hamadi (2021) in a study conducted in Nigeria came to conclusion to believe that causes and kinds of disciplinary problems faced by students determine the disciplinary measures to be undertaken. To the scholars, when teachers adopt rewards like praises and giving of rewards tokens, it helps the teacher to gain control of his class. Kindiki (2015) study in Kenya also found that teachers believe that the only way to manage student behaviour is through rewards or reinforcement because it has proven significant in several cases in discouraging wrong behaviour which leads to a conducive classroom environment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be deduced that drafting of classroom rules, changing of student's seat arrangement and rewards significantly relate with classroom control in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Hence, teachers' disciplinary techniques relate with classroom control in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following were recommended:

1. Teachers should continue to ensure that students are given the opportunity to participate in the drafting of the classroom rules, as it will help them to comply considering that they were part of those that made the rules.
2. Teachers should consolidate on disciplinary strategy like changing of student's seat arrangement, as it has proven to be effective in classroom control.
3. Teachers in collaboration with school management should always find ways to reward good students behaviour, in order to discourage wrong behaviours of some other students for effective classroom control.

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